

Earning Quality and Growth of Listed Firms in Nigeria

Akintoye, R.I., ★ Adegbe, F.F., ★★ Nwaobia, A.N., ★★★ and Kwarbai, J.D. ★★★★★

About the authors

All authors are affiliated with Babcock University, Department of Accounting Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria.

★ AKINTOYE, Rufus I. is a Professor of Accounting & Financial management.

★★ ADEGBIE, Festus F. is Head of Department, Department of Accounting and Associate professor of Taxation, fiscal policy & Accounting.

★★★ NWAOBIA, Apollos N. is Associate professor of Auditing and Financial reporting

★★★★ KWARBAI, Jerry D. is a Lecturer in the field of Auditing and financial reporting.

ABSTRACT

This paper investigated the effect of Earnings Quality (EQ) on the growth of manufacturing firms in Nigeria during the period 1996-2006 using an *ex-post* facto research design. We determined the earnings quality and growth of 26 listed firms in Nigeria. Our findings revealed that the quality of earnings had significant effect on Turnover Growth (TUG). However, earnings quality proxies had mixed effects because Earnings Predictability (EPRE) had a significant negative effect. The Value Relevance (VALR) and Accounting Conservatism (CONS) had a significant positive effect, while Accrual Quality (AQUA) had an insignificant negative effect on Turnover growth of firms. The study concludes that Earnings quality is useful in determining the growth of firms.

Keywords: Accrual quality, business growth, Conservatism, Earnings predictability, Value relevance

JEL code: D

CITATION:

Akintoye, R.I., Adegbe, F.F., Nwaobia, A.N., and Kwarbai, J.D. (2019). "Earning quality and growth of listed firms in Nigeria." *Inter. J. Res. Methodol. Soc. Sci.*, Vol., 5, No. 1: pp. 74-82. (Jan. – Mar. 2019); ISSN: 2415-0371. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2667486

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The health of a firm in a highly competitive business environment is dependent upon its capability of achieving profit and maintain financial solvency. When a firm loses competency to maintain profit and financial solvency, it becomes unhealthy and is in danger of business failure leading to total extinction (Akintoye, 2008; Wu, 2010). Since the growth of a business is reported or communicated to the providers of capital and other stakeholders through the financial reports, the reliability of figures presented in the financial report remain of paramount importance to users of

financial information. This is because information is demanded by investors in order to assess the timing and certainty of future cash flows to determine the level of growth over a given period of time. It can be argued that the extent to which business organizations report their activities especially as it has to do with finance, may be a factor that could influence business performance and growth of the business organization (Ojeka, Mukoro, Dick, & Kanu, 2015).

Adekunle and Asaolu (2006) identified in their study that financial reports and analysis presented by Nigerian companies have been found to be deficient over time and this is a great concern to investors as their performance in terms of profitability which are measured by turnover or the ratio of profit retention are decreasing by the day. Shehu and Ahmad (2013) also found that financial information quality in Nigeria remains weak compared to other advanced market, and this has resulted in hampering of the growth of efficient equity market. Hence, this study supports the view that if financial report is of good quality, it will affect profitability and business growth in the long run. Since investors are in need of information, quality information will increase the trading and subsequently growth and expansion of firms.

Our study is slightly related to other works, but is still distinct from prior studies that examined the link between earnings quality with short term performance (Kim, Lee & Choi, 2016; Narjess, Sadok & Walid, 2016; Nwaobia, Kwarbai, Jayeoba, & Ajibade, 2016; Solmaz & Mehdi 2015; Ojeka *et al.*, 2015) but not long term business growth considered pivotal to survival which is the focus of this study. In our view, if the quality of earning can impact the financial performance of, it should also impact the growth of firms. Hence, this study argues that the quality of accounting information can cause market reaction and induce growth and expansion of business on a long run. There is paucity of studies that looked at the direct link of Earnings quality and Business growth in Nigeria. The paper is organized into five sections including this introduction. Section 2 discusses review of literature and development of hypothesis on the effects of financial reporting quality and investor decision. Section 3 explains the methodology, including the choice of variables and their measurement. Estimation results are presented and discussed in Section 4 and Section 5 gives the conclusion.

2.0 LITERATURE

This section provides a review of the theoretical framework and Literature review on earnings quality and firms growth. We begin with the principles underlying this relationship then discuss the empirical literature on variables that affect firm's growth.

2.1 Theoretical Consideration

There are many theories that associate the corporate performance of firms and how internal and external variables affects it, some of which are agency theory, positive accounting theory and stewardship theory which were discussed in this paper (Akintoye *et al.*, 2016). The agency theory is the root and the building block of all corporate performance. It is believed to be the first theory to be considered once the issues of corporate performance appear in a discussion. According to them, this theory could be traced to the USA in the early 1970s. The agency relationship is one between one party (agent) and another, (the principal), where the agent is hired to act for the interest of the principal (Jensen and Meckling, 1976). The agency theory could explain the reason why management uses certain accounting policies to benefit themselves rather than maximizing shareholders wealth. Management incurs agency cost to reduce the activity of the management that is not in alignment with the investor's objectives. Alongside the agency theory is positive accounting theory that assumes that individuals are primarily motivated by self-interest with the aim to maximize their own wealth by selecting an accounting method that can suite their objective. Positive Accounting theory therefore explains the different motive for using different accounting policies and it can explain the sign of the effect on growth of firms as affected by the quality of earnings. We deduced that management can manipulate accounting information for several reasons aside in order to achieve their selfish desire. However, the stewardship theory, as proposed by

Friedman in 1970, negates the assumption of agency theory and positive accounting theory that directors will fulfill their duties towards the shareholders and assumes that human beings are good and the directors are trustworthy. Hence, the stewardship theory suggests that the stakeholder theory replaces the sole aim of maximizing the value of shareholders to include the satisfaction of all major stakeholders. This suggests that the management will make good choices that will bring about growth and expansion of the business.

2.2 Empirical Review and Hypothesis development

Several studies have attempted to analyze the effect of earning quality on different component of performance of corporate firms and the need to make appropriate disclosure for the use of investors performance (Kim *et al.*, 2016; Narjess *et al.*, 2016; Nwaobia *et al.*, 2016; Solmaz & Mehdi 2015; Ojeka *et al.*, 2015). For instance, Kim *et al.* (2016) highlighted that investor's demand information in order to assess the timing and uncertainty of current and future cash flow so that they may evaluate firms and make other investment decisions. The extent to which a firm reports its activities significantly impacts to its profitability and growth (McMahon, 1996).

Ghosh *et al.*, (2010) explored the effect of earnings quality and earnings response coefficients using turnover growth as proxy. They documented that earnings are of higher quality when growth in earnings is supported by revenue increases rather than through cost reductions. In their view revenue-supported earnings growth is likely to be more sustainable because revenue is the key value driver and its growth often reflects the underlying product differentiation strategy. Moshi (2016) evaluated the impact of earnings management on firm's financial performance in Tanzanian manufacturing companies and their findings showed that earnings management has negative impact on firm's financial performance. This was corroborated by the further findings that most of the firms managed the earnings, suggestive of lack quality and adequate disclosure.

Pranesh (2017) analyzed the nature and extent of earnings management practices on growth and performance of India firms. Regression analysis of the study showed that growth of the firm is positively associated with discretionary accruals while performance is negatively correlated. Nonetheless, among the other control variables viz firms' size and age were also found statistically significant influencing variables.

The relationship between earnings quality and firms growth in extant literature are mixed. For instance, Beaver (1968) research shows that growth opportunities provides managers with incentive to smooth earnings as earnings volatility increase perceived firm risk which adversely affect the cost of capital needed by the firm. Penman and Zhang, (2002) and Chan *et al.* (2006) documented an inverse relationship between the quality of earnings and growth firms. In their findings, sales or net operating assets are accompanied with lower earnings quality. Also Ma and Ma (2017) established a negative association between Chinese publically listed firm's performance and earnings quality, suggesting that the quality of earning exerts a negative effect on corporate performance.

The relationship between earnings quality and firm growth is not straightforward or conclusive. We join other researchers in the developed world to posit that the quality earnings will bring about growth of business. We therefore hypothesized that: ***The quality of earning affect the growth of firms in Nigeria.***

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The *ex-post facto* research design was adopted in this study. Secondary data were extracted from the annual reports and accounts of twenty six (26) companies for a period of 21 years (1996-2016) representing 546 firm-year observations. To achieve the objective of this paper, three variables were identified and discussed in this section. We defined dependent variable as the growth in turnover, independent variable as earnings quality, control variables are Age and size. First, in determining earning quality we used four proxies of earnings quality which are: earnings predictability by Francis *et al.* (2005), Value relevance by Feltham and Ohlson (1995), Accounting Conservatism

and accrual quality by Dechow and Dichev (2002), and modified by McNichols and Stubben (2008) and Kothari *et al.* (2005). Secondly, we analyze the effect of earnings quality on growth of firms in the Nigeria. Thirdly, we include Corporate Age and Corporate Size as control variables and analyze their influence on growth of firms.

Earnings quality is one of the most important accounting research topics of the last few decades. However there is neither an agreed-upon meaning of the concept nor a generally accepted approach to measuring earnings quality (Schipper and Vincent, 2003). Earnings quality is considered a multidimensional concept that is difficult to measure, and recent research evaluates various earnings attributes (Francis *et al.*, 2004; Dechow *et al.*, 2010).

We draw upon prior research to identify other factors that can affect the casualty of quality earnings and firms growth. We included Corporate Age and Corporate Size to the model According to Nwaobia *et al.*, (2016) size and age variables could be used to control for the economics factors that influence firm’s growth. The measurement procedures of these variables are shown in table 3.1 below.

Table 1. Variable measurement

Variables	Abbr	Definition
Earning Predictability	EPRE	According to Francis <i>et al</i> (2005), earnings predictability is measured using the square root of the error variance from Karmedi and Lipe’s (1987) model of earning persistence. First we will make autoregressive model AR(1) for annual earning $X_{j,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{j,t-1} + \varepsilon_{j,t}$ or the we use earnings persistence result as suggested by Francis <i>et al.</i> (2005) then take square root of the error variance of AR(1) $\sqrt{\sigma^2(\varepsilon_{j,t})}$
Conservatism	CONS	$CONS = \frac{MPS}{BVS}$ where BVS is Book value $BVS = \frac{\text{Net Asset value}}{\text{Total Outstanding Ordinary Share Capital}}$ MPS: The stock exchange market share price at the end of financial firm year
Value Relevance	VALR	Feltham and Ohlson (1995) presented a valuation model that, in contrast to Easton and Harris’s, explicitly relates the book values of equity and earnings with stock price. In statistical notation, the model is as follows: $MPS_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 BVS_{i,t} + \alpha_2 EPS_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$ where $MPS_{i,t}$ is the stock price of firm i at time t, $BVS_{i,t}$ is the book value of equity of firm i at time t, divided by common shares outstanding, and $EPS_{i,t}$ is Earnings per share of firm i at time t. The Feltham and Ohlson model was used in this study as it measures the mean annual level of statistical association between book values of equity, earnings, and stock prices. The Ohlson (1995) is chosen in this present study because it measures the long term relationship between accounting information measures and share prices.
Accrual quality	AQUA	Our accruals quality measure is derived from the Dechow and

		Dichev (2002), hereafter referred to as DD. The DD model is based on the extent to which working capital accruals map into cash flow realizations, where a poor match means low accruals quality. Therefore, we regress working capital accruals on prior, current, and future cash flows from operations $TCA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CFO_{it-1} + \beta_2 CFO_{it-1} + \beta_3 CFO_{it+1} + \beta_4 \Delta REV_{it} + PPE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$ where: $TCA_{it} = (\Delta CA_{it} - \Delta Cash_{it}) - (\Delta CL_{it} - \Delta STDBET_{it})$
TOG	Turnover growth	$\frac{\text{Current Turnover} - \text{Previous Turnover}}{\text{Previous Turnover}}$
CORPSIZE	Corporate Size	Estimated as natural logarithm of total assets
CORPAGE	Age of the firm	The age of a firm (AGE) is defined as the absolute number of years of incorporation

The Model specification

$$TOG = f(EPRE, AQUA, CONS, VAR, CORPAGE, CORPSIZE) \quad (1)$$

$$TOG_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 EPRE_{it} + \alpha_2 AQUA_{it} + \alpha_3 CONS_{it} + \alpha_4 VALR_{it} + \alpha_5 CORPAGE_{it} + \alpha_6 ORPSIZE_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (2)$$

4. ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics of the data. It presents the mean, maximum, minimum and standard deviation, from all quantifiable variables used in the model.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

VARIABLE	OBS	MEAN	SD	MIN	MAX
CORPAGE	546	43.615	15.318	10.000	93.000
CORPSIZE	546	6.828	1.053	4.036	10.014
TURNGRWT	546	2.238	43.011	-0.998	999.000
EPRE	546	-2.450	0.542	-2.888	11.307
EQUA	546	-7.730	60.290	-483.406	103.667
VARL	546	-58.922	384.946	-4685.825	2460.405
CONS	546	-427.132	13240.040	-262592.400	55490.000

From the reported descriptive statistics, corporate age (CORPAGE), the age of the sampled firms used are within the range 10 years to 93 year of existence. This indicates that the firms under consideration are experienced in their respective areas of business endeavors due to the long duration of their corporate existence. Firms reacts differently to how they prepare quality report according to their experience over time in the industry in which the operate. There is also an indication that sampled firms have large balance sheet size (CORPSIZE) using log of total asset as proxy. CORPSIZE has a minimum value of 4.036 billion and a maximum value of N10.14 billion, suggesting that the firms are large firms.

The descriptive statistics also shows that Turnover Growth (TUG) has a minimum value of -0.998 and maximum of 999.00. The mean and standard deviation value is 2.238 and 43.011, respectively. The minimum, maximum and standard deviation suggest a broad variation away from the mean and as such the variable is volatile in nature.

For earning predictability (EPRE), Accrual Quality (AQUA), Conservatism and Value relevance of accounting earnings, the minimum, maximum; mean and standard deviation suggest low variation. The mean value which is also lower than the standard deviation also indicates low variation for earning predictability.

4.2. Regression Result

Table 3. Regression Analysis with Driscoll-Kraay standard errors for Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
C	14.2092	1.6512	8.65	0.000*
EPRE	-2.1046	0.3005	-7.00	0.000*
VALR	0.0158	0.0017	9.01	0.000*
CONS	0.0010	0.0001	7.84	0.000*
AQUA	-1.30006	4.03006	-0.32	0.748
CORPAGE	-0.1078	0.0131	-8.20	0.000*
CORPSIZE	-1.5130	0.1682	-8.99	0.000*
R-squared	0.3904			
Adjusted R-squared	0.3820			
F-Statistic	46.83			
Prob.(F-Stat)	0.000*			
Diagnostic Tests	Statistics			
Hausman test	89.62			0.000*
Heteroskedasticity test	91689.30			0.000*
Wooldridge test for autocorrelation	1053.680			0.000*
Pesaran's test of cross sectional independence	7.309			0.000*

Dependent Variable: TUG; Obs.:546

*significant at 5%

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2018

The result of the post estimation tests on Table 4.2 shows that all the various tests are significant with probability values of 0.000, which is less than the acceptable 0.05 level of significance. Specifically, the significance of hausman test shows that the null hypothesis to estimate random effect was rejected; as such the model was tested for the appropriateness of random effect using the testparm option on stata. In addition, the Breusch-pagan heteroskedasticity test showed a p-value of 0.000, implying that the null hypothesis of constant variance was rejected and there is presence of heteroskedasticity. As such, if predictions are based on their regression estimates, it will be biased and inconsistent. Furthermore, the Wooldridge test for autocorrelation is significant at 5% which implies that there is presence of first-order autocorrelation. This indicates that the residuals are correlated over time. The Pesaran's test of cross sectional independence shows that the residuals are cross sectionally correlated at 5% level of significance. Thus, in line with Hoechle (2007), the presence of heteroskedasticity, first-order autocorrelation, and cross sectional dependence indicate the need to use Driscoll and Kraay standard errors to estimate the model to avoid estimation bias. Therefore, the model was estimated using Driscoll and Kraay standard errors.

4.3 Interpretation of Result and Discussions

The result of the regression analysis on Table 4.1 shows Earning Predictability (EPRE) and Accrual quality (AQUA) have negative effect on Turnover growth. This is indicated by the signs of the coefficients, that is $\alpha_1 = -2.104683 < 0$; $\alpha_2 = -1.30006 > 0$. This result is inconsistent with *a priori* expectation as it was expected that accounting base measures of Earnings Quality (EQ) will have positive effects on the growth of firms. However, VARL and CONS exerted positive effects on firms growth (that is $\alpha_3 = 0.0158 < 0$; $\alpha_4 = + 0.0010$) respectively. The control variables CORPAGE and CORPSIZE exerts negative effect on turnover growth as indicated by the coefficients $\alpha_5 = -$

0.1078783 <0; $\alpha_6 = -1.51308$. Likewise, the P-value of the individual t-statistics shows that Market base EQ measure have significant effects on Business growth at 5% level of significance acceptable in this study.

The adjusted R-squared showed that about 38% variations in Business growth can be attributed by the quality of earnings while the remaining 62% variation is caused by other factors not included in this model. Our explanatory variables suffered from series of transformation, we used the residual values of the earnings quality estimate according to Dechow and Dechev (2005) and this must have accounted for the low adjusted R-squared. To the best of our knowledge, there is no possible variable that was left out in the model as both market and accounting base measures of earnings quality were used. The coefficient of determination shows that the main model has average explanatory power. This is further emphasized by the probability of the F-statistic of 0.000 which shows that the regression result is statistically significant because this is less than 5%, the level of significance adopted for this study.

In addition, at the level of significance of 0.05, and F-statistics of 46.83 and p-value of 0.00, the null hypothesis that financial reporting quality has no significant effect on turnover growth of manufacturing firms in Nigeria is not accepted. Therefore, from the regression estimates, EQ measured by EPRE, AQUA, VALR and CONS jointly have significant positive effect on turnover growth of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

However, considering the individual coefficients separately, the regression analysis shows Earnings predictability and accrual quality had a negative significant and insignificant effect on turnover growth respectively, value relevance and conservatism had a positive and significance effect on turnover growth of Nigeria manufacturing firms. Our findings are consistent with the body of literatures that posit that quality of earnings improves the growth of businesses. Although, some argued that, a growing firm engages in earnings smoothing which reduces the quality of the reported earnings. As earlier indicate Beaver (1968) study shows that growth opportunities provides managers with incentive to smooth earnings as earnings volatility increase perceived firm risk which adversely affect the cost of capital needed by the firm. Our findings are consistent with Pranesh (2017) that growth of the firm is positively associated with discretionary accruals while performance is negatively correlated.

Pranesh (2017) also indicates that firm's size and age were statistically significant influencing variable on the relationship of earnings quality and firms performance, although our result indicates negative influence. This finding is in line with the work of Beyer (2008) that suggested that an investor wishes to transact with firms with growing turnover.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effect of Earnings quality on growth of listed firms in Nigeria. The model is statistically significant at 5% level of significance. Findings of this study provide insight into the effect of earnings quality on growth of firms in Nigeria. It further provide an insight as to the extent to which each of the independent variables of earnings quality influences the dependent variable of growth. It also provides an affirmation of the extent to which the variations in the dependent variable are caused by the independent variables covered in the models as depicted by the adjusted R-squared.

The study concluded that earnings quality is a predictor of firm growth and that firm size and age can influence the relationship between earnings quality and firm growth. The overall result of the regression analysis shows that earnings quality has a significant effect on growth of firms in Nigeria for the period under review although, the explanatory power is low but causality exists. The controlling variable used in the models also affects the relationship between earnings quality and firm's growth although depending on the association under consideration.

The study recommends that since aggressive earnings management reduces the quality of earnings, standard setters and regulators should curb creative accounting practices by removing loopholes in the use of judgments and managerial discretions in the estimation of assets and

liabilities. Managers should embrace ethical values in reporting through providing quality accounting information that reflect the actual activity of the firms to foster the confidence of investors and owner of business. At all times, managers should avoid aggressiveness earning management which connotes negative manipulation of accounting information.

REFERENCES

- Adekunle, A. A., & Asaolu, T. (2013). An empirical investigation of the financial reporting practices and banks 'stability in Nigeria. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, **2**(5), 157.
- Akintoye, I. R., Jayeoba, O. O., Ajibade, A. T., Olayinka, I. M., & Kwarbai, J.D (2016). Value of accounting numbers and analysts 'forecast errors. *International Journal of Research Methodology in Social Science*, **2**(3). 17-32.
- Akintoye, I.R (2008). Optimizing Investment Decisions through informative Accounting, *European Journal of Social Science*, **7**(3), 178-191
- Beaver, W. 1968. The information content of annual earnings announcements. *Journal of Accounting Research*. (Supplement): 67-92.
- Chan, K., Chan, L., Jegadeesh, L. and Lakonishok, J. (2006). Earnings Quality and Stock Returns”, *Journal of Business*, **79**, 1041–1082.
- Dechow, P., G W., & Schrand, C. (2010). Understanding earnings quality: A review of the proxies, their determinants and their consequences. *Journal of accounting and economics*, **50**(2-3), 344-401.
- Francis, J., LaFond, R., Olsson, P. and Schipper, K. (2004). Costs of equity and earnings attributes, *The Accounting Review*, **79**, 967–1010
- Ghosh, A., Gu, Z., & Jain, P. C. (2010). Sustained earnings and revenue growth, earnings quality, and earnings response coefficients. *Review of accounting studies*, **10**(1), 33-57.
- Gray, S., Meek, G., & Roberts, C.,. (1995). Factors influencing voluntary annual report disclosures by US, UK and continental European multinational corporations. *Journal of international business studies*, **26**(3), 555-572.
- Jensen, M.C. & Meckling W.H. (1976). “Theory of the firm: managerial behaviour, agency cost and ownership structure.” *Journal of Finance Economics* **3**(4). 305-360
- Kim, J., Lee, C. Y., & Cho, Y. (2016). Technological diversification, core-technology competence, and firm growth. *Research Policy*, **45**(1), 113-124.
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International.
- Ma, S., & Ma, L. (2017). The association of earnings quality with corporate performance: Evidence from the emerging market of China. *Pacific Accounting Review*, **29**(3), 397-422
- McMahon, R.G.(1996). Business growth and performance and the financial reporting practices of Australian manufacturing SMEs. School of commerce, *Journal of small Business management*. **39**(2), 152-164.
- Narjess, B, Sadok, E.; and Walid, S. (2015). Firms growth and political institutions, *Journal of Multidisciplinary Finanacial. Management* **31**.
- Nissim, D., & Ziv, A. (2001). Dividend changes and future profitability. *Journal of Finance*,**56**, 2111– 2133.
- Nwaobia, A.N, Kwarbai J.D, Jayeoba O.O, and Ajibade A.T (2016). Financial reporting Quality and investors decision. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Research*. **2**(7)140-147.
- Nwaobia, A. N., Kwarbai, J. D. and Ogundajo, G. O. (2016). Tax planning and firm value: Empirical evidence from Nigerian consumer goods industrial sector. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting* **7**(2). 172-183
- Ojeka, S.A., Mukoro A., Dick O. and Kanu, C. (2015). Does Financial Reporting Disclosures Enhance Firm Financial Performance in the Nigerian Manufacturing Companies? *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences, MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy* **6**(6).
- Penman, S. H. (2003). The quality of financial statements: Perspectives from the recent stock market bubble. *Accounting Horizons* **17**, 77-96.

- Pranesh, D. (2017) Assaying the Impact of Firm's Growth and Performance on Earnings Management: An Empirical Observation of Indian Economy. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management* **4**(2).
- Raymond, P. (2010). The relation between growth opportunities and earnings quality: A cross-sectional study about the quality of earnings for European firms with relatively high growth opportunities. *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting*. 1-19
- Schipper, K. and Vincent, L. (2003). Earnings quality", *Accounting Horizon*, **17**, (Supplement), 97–111.
- Shehu, U.,H and Ahmad B. (2013). Firm characteristics and Financial Reporting quality of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting, Banking and management* **1**(6) 47-63.
- Solmaz, H and Mehdi (2015). The sales growth and growth potential effect on financial reporting quality at listed companies in Tehran stock exchange. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (OMAN Chapter)* **4** (7).
- Wu, W. (2010). Beyond Business Failure Prediction. *Expert Syst. Appl.*, **37**: 2371-2376.